

THE BENEFITS OF OLIVE OIL FOR HUMAN HEALTH AND ITS USE IN COSMETOLOGY

B. M. Do'monov associate professor of Andijan State Pedagogical Institute

O. X. Ashiraliyeva teacher of Andijan State Pedagogical Institute

O'. Z. Tulanova teacher of Andijan State Pedagogical Institute

R. Q. Ne'matjonova student of Andijan State Pedagogical Institute

G. Sh. Abdullayeva student of Andijan State Pedagogical Institute

F. U. Latibjonova student of Andijan State Pedagogical Institute

Email: abdullayevagulxayo112@gmail.com

Annotation: This article contains information about the chemical composition of olive oil, a healing natural remedy familiar to all of us, about the benefits for human health, about its importance in cosmetology, about its useful specializations that we know and do not know about.

Keywords: olive oil, cosmetology, collagen, oleic acid, linoleic acid, stearic acid, vitamins.

Every woman wants to look beautiful and young, to stand out from the rest of course. But some cosmetics may not like all skins equally and give the expected result. There are such natural remedies that are more useful and effective than any cosmetics. In this article we will talk about olive oil, one of them.

If you know how to use olive oil in personal care, you can save a lot by reducing cosmetics. The oleic acid contained in olive oil stimulates collagen production, increases skin elasticity and promotes the penetration of other important ingredients into the skin.

The linoleic acid contained in its composition normalizes the water balance, as a result of which the problem of moisture is eliminated. Also this substance protects against the

harmful effects of ultraviolet radiation. Linoleic acid has an anti-inflammatory effect, it is even used in the treatment of eczema.

It also contains palmitic acid, a substance that activates the synthesis of collagen and elastin. Therefore, an olive oil face mask gives a good result for wrinkles.

Olive oil also contains stearic acid, which enhances the protective ability of the layers of the epidermis and has a wound healing effect. In addition, it contains vitamins A, E, K, which are well soluble in fat, some vitamins of Group B, healthy fats namely omega-3 and omega-6.

The lower the acidity level of olive oil (up to 0.8%), the higher the quality is considered[1].

Olive oil is useful not only for the skin, but also for the whole body. One of its most surprisingly useful specializations, confirmed by numerous studies, is that it reduces the risk of developing tumors of poor quality, especially breast cancer[3].

Olive oil is also good for the digestive system. It improves the functioning of the stomach, intestines, pancreas and liver, helps to heal ulcers of the stomach and duodenum. In addition, cardiovascular diseases are a natural remedy to prevent heart attacks in particular, as well as cancer[5].

➤ **Olive oil as a refreshing agent**

Consuming 1 cup of water and half a teaspoon of olive oil with lemon juice can help improve your well-being as well as stimulate the digestive system[2].

➤ **To get rid of excess weight**

Drinking 1 teaspoon of olive oil half an hour before breakfast will give a feeling of satiety, which will prevent you from overeating.

➤ **For the purpose of constipation**

It is necessary to drink 1 tablespoon of oil on an empty stomach for a week, after which it is recommended to take a break and, if necessary, continue the course.

➤ To improve the condition of hair and skin

It is consumed on an empty stomach, adding 50 ml of Olives to 1 cup of honey and half a glass of lemon juice. Also, olive oil is rubbed into the skin and applied as a mask.

➤ As an ointment for lips

When the lips are chapped, they should be rubbed with the same amount of olive oil and bee wax, stirring to bring them back to normal and speed up its recovery, the treatment should be repeated 1-2 times.

Attention! It is recommended that you do not use olive oil carelessly, do not consume too much. After all, the Meyor of everything is good.

Used literature

1. O. N. Imomov. “O‘zbekistonning foydali o‘simliklari modulidan o‘quv-uslubiy majmua”- Namangan.: 2021, 105-bet
2. [www.avitsenna.uz](https://avitsenna.uz) “<https://avitsenna.uz/zaytun-yogi/>”
3. [www.med360.uz](https://med360.uz) “<https://med360.uz/salomatlik/zaytun-yogi-foydasi/>”
4. www.minikari.ru
5. [www.shifo.uz](https://shifo.uz) “<https://shifo.uz/article/zaytun-yogi/>”